

Research Article

Norovirus gastroenteritis associated with food served by housewives at home in Bihar, India: A Case-control study

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Abstract

A retrospective case-control study was undertaken between the 17th and 24th of 2022, with participants including patients (housewives) admitted to the hospital. All the patients in hospital are from local region and are housewives. The main sources of this Norovirus infection are from the unhygienic kitchen. Unhygienic utensils in the kitchen, inadequate food storage and improper waste disposal were identified. Investigation showed that women in kitchen used tap water for cooking but used untreated ground water to wash food ingredients and utensils. Questionnaires were returned from 35 attendees, out of total 46 questionnaires distributed (response rate 76 %). Thirty-Five cases (including 15 confirmed cases) and 45 controls were identified and interviewed (Control cases are of same age and sex of confirmed cases). All cases were aged 10–30 years old, are 35 females. We have randomly selected the 45 participants for control group. 15 of the 35 stool specimens were positive for GII Norovirus. Other stool samples tested were negative for bacterial pathogens. To detect the Norovirus, Real-time Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction testing was conducted. By prioritizing and consistently implementing robust hand washing and utensil washing protocols, food service establishments can significantly reduce the risk of Norovirus transmission in the kitchen environment. This, combined with other sanitation and hygiene measures, can contribute to a comprehensive strategy for preventing Norovirus outbreaks and ensuring food safety. An improved vaccine development and implementation of interventions is the need for the eradication of Norovirus.

Keywords: Norovirus, RT-PCR: Reverse transcription, vomiting, diarrhoea, nausea, myalgia and lowgrade fever, sanitation and hygiene.

Introduction

Globally, norovirus is detected in an estimated 18% of cases of acute gastroenteritis (AGE) [1] and causes approximately 214,000 deaths each year [27]. The World Bank list of economies classified 81 countries as LMIC (Lower-Middle-Income Countries) and LIC (Lower-Income Countries) in June 2018. Of these, 29 were represented in this review of norovirus prevalence and diversity in low-resource countries. Overall, 36,288 symptomatic gastroenteritis cases were tested for norovirus in 64 studies over a period of 19 years. Twenty-three of the 64 studies tested 5310 healthy controls for norovirus. Across all ages, norovirus was detected in 14% (95% CI 14–15, 5158/36288) of symptomatic cases and in 8% (95% CI 7–9, 423/5310) of healthy control subjects. This correlates with previous global prevalence estimates of 14% (95% CI 11–16) in symptomatic cases in high-mortality developing countries and 7% (95% CI 3–10) in asymptomatic controls [1]. When countries were grouped according to income, norovirus was detected across all ages in 11% (95% CI 11–12) of symptomatic cases and 9% (95% CI 8–10) of asymptomatic controls in LIC. Noroviruses (NoV), a single-stranded RNA virus in the genus *Norovirus* of the *Caliciviridae* family, is one of the major pathogens causing outbreaks of acute gastroenteritis [23]. NoV is highly contagious, stable outside of the host and the lack of long-lasting immunity of the host; thus, it usually results in high attack rate [24, 25]. The detection rate for both symptomatic and asymptomatic norovirus infections in LIC was higher than the 6% (95% CI 3–10) and 5% (95% CI 4–8) estimated previously [2]. A person can experience an average of three to eight episodes of norovirus illness in their lifetime, with at least one occurring by the age of five [4]. Noroviruses are a leading cause of sporadic cases and outbreaks of acute gastroenteritis among adults and children, with a substantial impact on public health globally [3,4]. It can be classified into six genogroups (GI–GVI), three of which (GI, GII, and GIV) cause human disease [5].

Strains of GII.4 genotype have caused 70–80% of all reported outbreaks over the past 13 years [6], and have become the most common cause of outbreaks. Norovirus is transmitted via the faecal–oral route primarily through close contact with an infected person, contact with contaminated fomites or consumption of contaminated food or water.[7] The average incubation period is between 24 and 48 hours, with symptoms including acute onset vomiting, diarrhoea, nausea, myalgia and lowgrade fever.[8] Infected individuals shed the virus while symptomatic; however, shedding has been documented before the onset of symptoms, after symptoms have resolved and by asymptomatic infected individuals.[9-11] Contamination of food by both symptomatic and asymptomatic infected food handlers has been well documented.[12-18]

Fecal-oral spread is the primary route of norovirus transmission, and humans can also be infected by direct person-to-person contact, consumption of contaminated food or water, or contact with contaminated environmental surfaces [19]. Foodborne transmission is an important source in the global spread of Norovirus [20,21]. The patients in hospital are from local region and the females are housewife (Food handlers). The main sources of this Norovirus infection are from the unhygienic kitchen. Unhygienic utensils in the kitchen, inadequate food storage and improper waste disposal were identified. Investigation showed that womens in kitchen used tap water for cooking but used untreated ground water to wash food ingredients and utensils. Aim of present study is to investigate the epidemiology of Norovirus by food handlers in kitchen (i.e.by Housewives).

Ethics Statement: The Institutional Ethics Committee of Shree Narayan Medical Institute and Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, India, has approved this study. Signed consent forms were obtained from all participants.

Methods and Data Collection

A retrospective case-control study was undertaken between the 17th and 24th of July,

2022, with participants including patients (housewives) admitted to the hospital. Cases were found using a standard epidemiological questionnaire. Trained investigators took part in the survey to investigate the probable method of transmission. The control group consisted of healthy housewives of the same age as the case, but who did not have gastrointestinal problems. The research population for this epidemic included both suspected and confirmed cases. suspected cases included one of the following Two symptoms: 1) Diarrhea (< 3-4 times/day with changes in stool properties) and vomiting; 2) Vomiting more than twice in 24 hours since July 17, 2022. Confirmed cases were those with positive norovirus test findings using reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR). Questionnaires were returned by 35 participants out of 46 issued (76%) .Thirty-five

cases (15 confirmed cases) and 45 controls were identified and interviewed. Demographic data were collected (Geographical Region, age), symptoms (nausea, vomiting, Severity of Diarrhea, abdominal pain, headache, Restless and fever). All patients were between 10 and 30 years old, with 35 females / housewives. We have randomly selected the participants as control are 45. We used the Qiagen OneStep RT-PCR Kit to amplify the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) fragment of norovirus and the primer was used for this investigation.

Statistical analysis:

Data collected were analyzed using Excel, version 2010 (Microsoft) a p-value <0.05 was considered significant, Odds ratios (OR) with 95 % confidence intervals (CI) were calculated

Table 1: Distribution and association with demographic and clinical symptoms variables From July 17, 2022.

Variables		Total frequency (N=35)	%	Control (N=45)	%
Geographical region	Rural	22	62.85	25	55.55
	Urban	13	37.14	20	44.44
Gender	Male	00	0	0	--
	Female	35	100	35	100
Age	From 10 to 18Years	25	71.42	29	64.44
	Age 18-30	10	28.57	16	35.55
Diarrhoea	upto 6 times within24 h	19	54.28	35	77.77
	More than 6 times within 24 h	16	45.71	10	22.22
Vomiting	No	12	34.28	37	82.22
	Yes	23	65.71	8	17.77
Nausea	upto 3 days	20	57.14	31	68.88
	more than 3 days	15	42.85	14	31.11
Fever	No	20	57.14	32	71.11
	Yes	15	42.85	13	28.88
abdominal pain	No	30	85.71	29	64.44
	Yes	5	14.28	16	35.55
Restless	No	19	54.28	40	88.88
	Yes	16	45.71	5	4.44
Headache	No	14	40	26	57.77
	Yes	21	60	19	42.22

Environmental and laboratory investigation

Molecular detection of norovirus in food samples is costly, time-consuming, and sometimes ineffective due to the uneven dispersion of virus particles in foods [26]. Real-time Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction testing, Qiagen OneStep RT-PCR Kit to amplify the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) fragment of norovirus to detect GII norovirus in 15 out of 35 stool samples. The remaining stool samples tested negative for bacterial pathogens [22,23]. According to the guidelines published in the United States, the measure of infection control includes discarding exposed materials from vomiting and environmental decontamination of all surface areas within at least a 25-foot radius of the vomiting site, with temporary closure of the area where the vomiting incidence occurred and the toilet in the facility until the contaminated area is properly disinfected with bleach solution [23]. The environmental investigation revealed some of the handwashing facilities in food preparation areas were obstructed and not supplied with soap.

Discussion and Conclusion

The Norovirus contamination risks within kitchen environments, implementing targeted interventions, fostering collaborative efforts, and empowering both food handlers and consumers, the public health impact of Norovirus can be significantly reduced, leading to safer food preparation and consumption practices. Our investigation has the following limitations. By prioritizing and consistently implementing robust hand washing and utensil washing protocols, food service establishments can significantly reduce the risk of Norovirus transmission in the kitchen environment. This, combined with other sanitation and hygiene measures, can contribute to a comprehensive strategy for preventing Norovirus outbreaks and ensuring food safety. First, despite the fact that the survey was completed within one week, the study was retrospective in nature. We clarified the facts of a Norovirus infectious

diarrhea epidemic based on clinical symptoms, epidemiological features, and laboratory findings. Food handling practices are insufficient and unsanitary, which increases the likelihood of acute gastroenteritis outbreaks. Symptomatic food handlers are not allowed to work with food for 48 hours after remission of symptoms [15]. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to have identified Norovirus as the causative agent in a food handling practices of housewives in India. In such a case, it would be impossible to avoid epidemics by monitoring the health of housewives. As a result, implementing stringent hygiene standards such as thorough hand washing and wearing gloves while preparing meals, particularly hand-prepared and ready-to-eat foods, is critical to reducing the risk of food contamination from food handlers with asymptomatic norovirus infection. To limit the spread of Norovirus, more care should be used when handling food and other dietary items both at home and outdoors. To reduce food contamination, stringent general hygiene requirements, such as full hand washing and the use of gloves and protective clothing in kitchens, should be implemented. Furthermore, further study into managing Norovirus outbreaks should be conducted, including environmental cleaning of the location where Norovirus-infected patients lived, in order to avoid a major number of cases during outbreaks in India. Norovirus eradication need enhanced vaccine development and intervention implementation.

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Availability of data and materials: Data are however available from the authors upon reasonable request

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The Institutional Ethics Committee of Shree Narayan Medical Institute and Hospital,

Saharsa, Bihar, India, has approved this study. Signed consent forms were obtained from all participants.

Competing interests: The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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